

الحمد لله الرحمن الرحيم

**UNIVERSITY
OF MALAYA**

The Leader in Research & Innovation

Measuring Research Impact

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www.researcherid.com/rid/C-2414-2009
<http://scholar.google.com/citations>

22nd July 2016

All of my presentations are available online at:

https://figshare.com/authors/Nader_Ale_Ebrahim/100797

Link to this presentation: <https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.3493697.v1>

Measuring Research Impact

Keynote presentation at the 4th International Conference on
Researches in Science and Technology ([ICRST](#)),
21-22 July 2016, Kuala Lumpur

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www.researcherid.com/rid/C-2414-2009

<http://scholar.google.com/citations>

Abstract

Abstract: The activity of measuring and describing the impact of academic research is becoming increasingly important around the world. We need tools to measure research impact. **Bibliometrics** as a tool statistically analysis of publications. Bibliometrics has focused on the quantitative analysis of citations and citation counts which is complex. It is so complex and specialized that personal knowledge and experience are insufficient tools for understanding trends for making decisions. However, the reach of a publication can no longer be judged exclusively by the number of **times it is cited**. Because, we are now in the digital and sharing information age, academic conversations are as likely to be found on various academic social networks. So, we need new tools to measure the research impact. Altmetrics are new metrics proposed as alternatives to Impact Factor for journals and personal citation indexes like h-index. Altmetrics attempts to use the online activity to measure impact, buzz, word of mouth for scientific information and it includes **new ways to measure** usage at the citation level.

Keywords: Altmetric, H-index, Improve citations, Research tools, Bibliometrics, Research Visibility

Top 10 authors with the highest profile view counts on ResearchGate

Table 11. Top 10 authors with the highest profile view counts on ResearchGate (9th of November, 2015), compared to the same indicator on the 10th of September, 2015.

AUTHOR NAME	SEPTEMBER 10 th	NOVEMBER 9 th	MISMATCH (%)
	(2015) PROFILE VIEWS	(2015) PROFILE VIEW	
Nader Ale Ebrahim	19,821	13,281	67.00
Chaomei Chen	7,760	3,937	50.73
Loet Leydesdorff	4,227	1,758	41.59
Bakthavachalam Elango	2,883	1,756	60.91
Zaida Chinchilla	5,840	1,569	26.87
Mike Thelwall	4,297	1,568	36.49
Lutz Bornmann	3,129	1,439	45.99
Wolfgang Glänzel	3,012	1,301	43.19
Kevin Boyack	3,256	1,135	34.86
Peter Ingwersen	2,335	1,025	43.90

Source: Martín-Martín, A., Orduna-Malea, E., Ayllón, J. M., & López-Cózar, E. D. (2016). The counting house, measuring those who count: Presence of Bibliometrics, Scientometrics, Informetrics, Webometrics and Altmetrics in Google Scholar Citations, ResearcherID, ResearchGate, Mendeley, & Twitter. *EC3 Reseach Group: Evaluación de la Ciencia y de la Comunicación Científica Universidad de Granada and Universidad Politécnica de Valencia (Spain), In Progress*. doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.4814.4402

March 2016 Top 100 Technology Experts to Follow on Twitter

		#22) @computerworlduk - Computerworld UK (#22 last month)
	#23) @Tesseract257 - Tesseract257 (Down from #21)	
	#24) @FouadAkkad - Fouad Akkad (Up from #28)	
	#25) @elearningpros - Unlimited (Down from #24)	
	#26) @bbvaOpenMind - OpenMind (Down from #25)	
	#27) @SteveKuzj - Steve Kuzj (Up from #33)	
	#28) @AskDyson - Ask Dyson (Up from #29)	
	#29) @aleebrahim - Nader Ale Ebrahim (Up from #31)	

Altmetric Ambassador of the Month: Nader Ale Ebrahim

Our Ambassador of the Month for September is [Nader Ale Ebrahim](#), a visiting research fellow at the University of Malaya. He has run over 100 workshops for researchers in Malaysia, and is considered an authority on research promotion practices and metrics tools. [Learn more about what Nader has done so far as an Altmetric Ambassador on our blog.](#)

Research Tools Mind Map

Measuring your research impact: Getting Started

Cornell University
Library

Cornell / LibGuides / Measuring your research impact / Getting Started

Measuring your research impact: Getting Started

This guide provides an introduction to the various metrics used to measure researcher and journal impact.

Getting Started

Author Impact ▾

Journal Impact ▾

Tracking and Measuring Your Impact ▾

Broadening your impact

Table of Contents

Getting Started

Author Impact

H-index

G-index

i10-index

Journal Impact

Journal Citation Reports
(JCR)

Eigenfactor and Article

Getting Started

This guide details various ways of measuring research impact, particularly through traditional means of publishing and citation. Before you begin to delve into the various citation metrics, we recommend you do the following three things:

- **Sign up for an ORCID Identifier:** The Open Researcher Community ID is an increasingly recognized persistent digital identifier. The unique number assigned to you will allow publishers and aggregators of scholarly literature to distinguish you from researchers with similar names. This is a powerful tool in author disambiguation and it takes just a few minutes to sign up. Go to orcid.cornell.edu and follow the instructions to register for your ORCID identifier or to connect an existing ORCID account to your Cornell NetID. Have questions? Contact orcid-help@cornell.edu or visit [this guide](#) for more information about getting started.

Contact Information

Erin Eldermire

Email Me

From submission to sharing: the life cycle of an article

- **Phase 1: Conception and birth**
- **Phase 2: Submission**
- **Phase 3: Reviewers**
- **Phase 4: Production and publication**
- **Phase 5: Dissemination and archiving**
 - The article is published, but its life cycle isn't yet complete. In this phase, dissemination can start; sharing the [Share Links](#) article helps increase readership and make it more visible.

Research impact

- # of and value of Grants awarded
- # of awards (e.g. Nobel Prizes)
- Peer evaluation
- Publication counts
- Citation counts/citation metrics
 - Citation metrics are one piece of the research performance puzzle.
- Combination of factors
 - None of these measure works perfectly on its own, there are always anomalies and human judgment is required to interpret the results

What it's like being a researcher

What were your recent projects?

Where is your research based?

Does it have an impact?

What's next?

ing
h!

Where are your publications?

Are they accessible?

Is the research open access?

How do you pay the research?

Was it received?

WILL IT HAVE ANY IMPACT?

Did it have any impact?

What did you do with the grant income you received?
How did you cost your overheads?

are you supervising?
Does it have any IMPACT?

Research Impact Guide

Source: <http://subjectguides.library.unsw.edu.au/researchimpact>

UNSW
AUSTRALIA

Impact

usage

downloads
views

peer-review

expert opinion

citations

alt-metrics

storage
links
bookmarks
conversations

Source: <http://altmetrics.org/manifesto/>

Informetrics, scientometrics, bibliometrics, webometrics, cybermetrics and altmetrics

Source: Onyancha, Omwoyo Bosire. "Can informetrics shape biomedical research? A case study of the HIV/AIDS research in sub-Saharan Africa 1." *Inkanyiso: Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 6.1 (2014): 49-65.

Frequently Used Terms for Research Evaluation Metrics

Term	Short Definition
Bibliometrics	Bibliometrics is a set of methods to quantitatively analyse academic literature and scholarly communications.
Informetrics	Informetrics is the study of quantitative aspects of information. This includes the production, dissemination, and use of all forms of information, regardless of its form or origin.
Scientometrics	Scientometrics is the study of quantitative features and characteristics of science, scientific research and scholarly communications.
Webometrics	Webometrics is the study of quantitative features, characteristics, structure and usage patterns of the world wide web, its hyperlinks and internet resources.
Cybermetrics	Cybermetrics is an alternative term for Webometrics.
Librametrics	Librametrics is a set of methods to quantitatively analyse availability of documents in libraries, their usage and impact of library services to its user community.
Patentometrics	Patentometrics is a set of methods to quantitatively analyse patent databases, patent citations and their usage patterns.
Altmetrics	Altmetrics is new metrics proposed as an alternative to the widely used journal impact factor and personal citation indices like the h-index. The term altmetrics was proposed in 2010, as a generalization of article level metrics, and has its roots in the twitter #altmetrics hashtag.
Article Level Metrics (ALM)	Article level metrics is an alternative term for Altmetrics.

Source: Das, A.-K. (2015). [Research Evaluation Metrics](#). 7, place de Fontenoy, 75352 Paris 07 SP, France: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

Reasons for bibliometric studies

- Understanding of ***patterns***
 - discovery of regularities, behavior
 - “order out of documentary chaos” [Bradford, 1948]
- Analysis of ***structures & dynamics***
 - discovery of connections, relations, networks
 - search for regularities - possible predictions
- Discovery of ***impacts, effects***
 - relation between entities & amounts of their various uses
 - providing support for making of decisions, policies

Major Citation Databases

Name of Citation Database	Launched	Scope	Owned by	Terms of Availability
<i>Scopus</i>	2004	Global	Elsevier B.V.	Subscription-based
Google Scholar Citations	2004	Global	Google Inc.	Freely Available Online
Microsoft Academic Search	2003	Global	Microsoft Research	Freely Available Online
CiteSeerX (CiteSeerX.ist.psu.edu)	1997	Global; Subject specific	Pennsylvania State University, USA	Freely Available Online

Source: Das, A.-K. (2015). [Research Evaluation Metrics](#). 7, place de Fontenoy, 75352 Paris 07 SP, France: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

A Comparison between Two Main Academic Literature Collections: Web of Science and Scopus Databases

Author Level Indicators

Source: Das, A.-K. (2015). [Research Evaluation Metrics](#). 7, place de Fontenoy, 75352 Paris 07 SP, France: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

Citations as a proxy of scientific impact

World Report

Data by country

Subject Bubble Chart - US

Click on one or more subject areas ↑ to filter subject categories ↓

Technology Management and Virtual Teams

SciVal

Scopus

SciVal

Nader Ale Ebrahim

Help

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Collaboration

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My SciVal

Hide tags

Institutions and Groups

Researchers and Groups

Publication Sets

Countries and Groups

Research Areas

Technology Management and Virtual Teams

Technonogy Management, Virtual teams

"Virtual Teams" Research Area -

12 January 2015

Virtual teams

Bibliometrics

Bibliometrics, Citation

Add Research Areas

Remove all entities from this section

Technology Management and Virtual Teams

Source: Scopus data up to 16 Nov 2015

2010 to >2015

no filter selected

Summary

Institutions

Countries

Authors

Journals

Keyphrases

Overall research performance

Export

Scholarly Output
388

View list of publications

Views Count
15,084

Source: Scopus | Change

Field-Weighted Citation Impact
0.63

Citation Count
781

Keyphrase analysis

Top 50 keyphrases by relevance, based on 388 publications | Learn about keyphrase calculations

Bibliometrics

SciVal

Scopus

SciVal

Nader Ale Ebrahim ▾

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Research Areas

● Bibliometrics

Bibliometrics 🔒, *Citation* 🔒

○ "Virtual Teams" Research Area -

12 January 2015

Virtual teams

○ Physics Education - 13 January

2015

Physics Education

+ Add Research Areas

✖ Remove all entities from this section

Bibliometrics

Source: Scopus data up to 16 Nov 2015

2010 to >2015 ▾

no filter selected ▾

Summary

Institutions

Countries

Authors

Journals

Keyphrases

Overall research performance

Exp

Scholarly Output ⚙️

870

View list of publications

Views Count

22,401

Source: Scopus | Change

Field-Weighted Citation Impact ⚙️

1.72

Citation Count ⚙️

4,501

Keyphrase analysis

Top 50 keyphrases by relevance, based on 870 publications | [Learn about keyphrase calculations](#)

SCOPUS - Analyze author output

Combined data for multiple authors

Ebrahim, Nader Ale; Ale Ebrahim, Nader

[Back to citation overview](#)

Documents (18) *h*-index (6) **Citations (118)** Co-authors (33)

Analyze documents published between: 2009 to 2015 [Update Graph](#)

Year ▾	Citations
2016	1
2015	23
2014	33
2013	23
2012	18
2011	14
2010	6
2009	0

Citations by year

SciVal - Elsevier Research Intelligence

SciVal

Scopus SciVal | Nader Ale Ebrahim ▾ Help ▾

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Researchers and Groups

● Ale Ebrahim, Nader

Bibliometrics 🗄️, *Citation* 🗄️, *Research*

Tools 🗄️, *Virtual teams*

+ Add Researchers and Groups

x Remove all entities from this section

Publication Sets ▾

Countries and Groups ▾

Research Areas ▾

Ale Ebrahim, Nader

🇲🇾 University of Malaya | [View this Researcher in Scopus](#)

Source: Scopus data up to 16 Oct 2015

2010 to >2015 ▾

no filter selected ▾

Summary

Publications

Citations

Collaboration

Overall

Top collaborating Institutions

Collaboration ⚙️

Shortcuts ▾

Publications of Ale Ebrahim, Nader, by amount of international, national and institutional collaboration

Metric	Publications	Field-Weighted Citation Impact ▾
International collaboration	8	4.98
Only national collaboration	2	0.00
Only institutional collaboration	3	0.04
Single authorship (no collaboration)	0	-

Results: 1,218*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*You searched for: TOPIC: ("virtual team**") ...[More](#) [Create Alert](#)**Refine Results**

Search within results for...

Web of Science Categories ▾

- MANAGEMENT (458)
- COMPUTER SCIENCE
INFORMATION SYSTEMS (272)
- INFORMATION SCIENCE LIBRARY
SCIENCE (177)
- BUSINESS (172)
- COMPUTER SCIENCE
INTERDISCIPLINARY
APPLICATIONS (118)

[more options / values...](#)Sort by: **Publication Date -- newest to oldest** ▾◀ Page of 122 Select Page

Save to EndNote online ▾

[Add to Marked List](#)

1. **Leading Effective Global **Virtual Teams**: The Consequences of Methods of Communication**
By: Morgan, Lisa; Paucar-Caceres, Alberto; Wright, Gillian
SYSTEMIC PRACTICE AND ACTION RESEARCH Volume: 27 Issue: 6 Pages: 607-624 Published: DEC 2014

[Full Text from Publisher](#)[View Abstract](#)

2. **Understanding the attitudes, knowledge sharing behaviors and task performance of core developers: A longitudinal study**
By: Licorish, Sherlock A.; MacDonell, Stephen G.
INFORMATION AND SOFTWARE TECHNOLOGY Volume: 56 Issue: 12 Special Issue: SI Pages: 1578-1596
Published: DEC 2014

[Full Text from Publisher](#)[View Abstract](#)

3. **A Calibrated Group Decision Process**
By: Rokou, Elena; Kirytopoulos, Konstantinos
GROUP DECISION AND NEGOTIATION Volume: 23 Issue: 6 Special Issue: SI Pages: 1369-1384 Published:
NOV 2014

[Full Text from Publisher](#)[View Abstract](#)

4. **Satisfaction with outcome and process from web-based meetings for idea generation and**

[Analyze Results](#)[Create Citation Report](#)Times Cited: 0
*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*Times Cited: 0
*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*Times Cited: 0
*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*Times Cited: 0
(from Web of Science Core Collection)

Citation Report: 1218*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*You searched for: TOPIC: ("virtual team*") [...More](#)

This report reflects citations to source items indexed within Web of Science Core Collection. Perform a Cited Reference Search to include citations to items not indexed within Web of Science Core Collection.

Published Items in Each Year

The latest 20 years are displayed.

[View a graph with all years.](#)**Citations in Each Year**

The latest 20 years are displayed.

[View a graph with all years.](#)

Results found: 1218

Sum of the Times Cited [?]: 15217

Sum of Times Cited without self-citations [?]: 10399

Citing Articles [?]: 8040

Citing Articles without self-citations [?]: 7210

Average Citations per Item [?]: 12.49

h-index [?]: 58

DATA DRILL DOWN: CITATION TRENDS

Users can view citation trends for any entity in the rankings list. For example, if the user clicks on the name CHINESE ACAD SCI:

					Customize Indicators
Institutions	Web of Science Documents	Cites ▾	Cites/Paper	Top Papers	
1 CHINESE ACAD SCI	49,023	618,315	12.61		750
2 UNIV CALIF SYSTEM	19,690	497,452	25.26		772
3 US DEPT ENERGY	19,077	391,755	20.54		575
4 MAX PLANCK SOCIETY	12,151	248,622	20.46		317
5 SWISS FEDERAL INSTITUTES OF TECHNOLOGY DOMAIN	10,535	218,033	20.70		261
6 CSIR INDIA	16,332	198,253	12.14		119
7 CSIC	12,694	191,371	15.08		184
8 KYOTO UNIV	9,198	161,807	17.59		139
9 RUSSIAN ACAD SCI	38,236	159,575	4.17		44
10 UNIV CALIF	5,000	157,810	31.56		100

DATA DRILL DOWN: CITATION TRENDS

They will be taken to the Citation Trends Page for the Chinese Academy of Sciences, which shows a trend graph, normalized citation data, and raw citation data:

Practical Advice

- Find out what's Hot
 - <http://info.scopus.com/topcited/>
 - <http://top25.sciencedirect.com/>
 - Find the trends of the subject area
 - Search tips (including alerts)
 - Journals, authors, publications per year (Scopus)
 - Evaluate which journal is right for your article
 - Impact Factor
 - Subject Specific Impact Factor (<http://tinyurl.com/scopusimpact>)
 - SCImago Journal & Country Ranking (<http://scimagojr.com/>)
 - Journal Analyzer
 - *h*-Index
 - Find out more about the journals
 - Who are the editors?
 - Guide for authors
 - Article of the future
- <http://beta.cell.com/erickson/>

IF

SJR

SCImago
Journal & Country
Rank

Your paper is worthless if no one reads, uses, or cites it

A research study is meaningful **only if...**

- it is clearly described, so
- someone else can use it in his/her studies
- it arouses other scientists' interest and
- allows others to reproduce the results.

By submitting a manuscript you are basically trying to sell your work to your community...

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861 downloads within 24 hours of the first tweet about a paper

Maximising the impact of academic research

THE LONDON SCHOOL
OF ECONOMICS AND
POLITICAL SCIENCE

THE
IMPACT
BLOG

Home About Latest Research Book Series Resources LSE Comment Popular

Who gives a tweet? After 24 hours and 860 downloads, we think quite a few actually do

Earlier this year, the National Centre for Research Methods released a research paper to waves of interest from academics and researchers alike on Twitter. **Kaisa Puustinen** and **Rosalind Edwards** watched the number of downloads rise rapidly as the paper was passed around through the social media channel.

Students, early career researchers and established academics may all ponder about how many interviews will be enough when designing their research projects. Sarah Elsie Baker from Middlesex University and Rosalind Edwards from NCRM decided to tackle this subject and

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Popular Posts This Week

861 downloads within 24 hours of the first tweet about a paper

- The paper was uploaded online late afternoon on Monday 26th March and was first tweeted to our followers the following day. The paper caught the interest of NCRM Twitter followers and within 24h it was retweeted 10 times to over 5000 followers and shared 135 times using social sharing tools (email, microblogging, social bookmarking, social networking) available on NCRM website. This resulted in 861 downloads within 24 hours of the first tweet about our paper. This was clearly a Twitter effect, as the paper was not publicised anywhere else at that time.

How is the Altmetric score calculated?

The score is a weighted count

The score is derived from an automated algorithm, and represents a weighted count of the amount of attention we've picked up for a research output. Why is it weighted? To reflect the relative reach of each type of source. It's easy to imagine that the average newspaper story is more likely to bring attention to the research output than the average tweet. This is reflected in the default weightings:

News	8
Blogs	5
Twitter	1
Facebook	0.25
Sina Weibo	1
Wikipedia	3
Policy Documents (per source)	3
Q&A	0.25
F1000/Publons/Pubpeer	1
YouTube	0.25
Reddit/Pinterest	0.25
LinkedIn	0.5

“Alternative Metrics” Tools

- Altmetric.com

- Impactstory.org

- Plumanalytics.com

ImpactStory.

- PLoS Article-Level Metrics

- Usage Count (webofknowledge.com)

- Bookmetrix (<http://www.bookmetrix.com>)

- Article Metrics in Scopus

Altmetrics

- Altmetrics are new metrics proposed as alternatives to Impact Factor for journals and personal citation indexes like h-index. The term "article level metrics" was first put forward in 2010, but altmetrics (derived from "alternative metrics") become prevalent as it better suggested a range of new metrics. Altmetrics can be applied not only to articles but also to people, journals, books, data sets, web pages, etc. Many aspects of the impact of a work (such as article views, downloads, mentions in social media and new services) can be measured, as well as traditional citation counts.

Nader Ale Ebrahim

University of Malaya Visiting Research Fellow

 2

OVERVIEW

ACHIEVEMENTS

MENTIONS

PUBLICATIONS

ACHIEVEMENTS

[view all](#)

Global Reach ⁸²

Your research has been discussed in 15 countries. That's high: only 17% of researchers have their work as widely discussed.

 Your tweeters come from Austria, Brazil, Canada and 12 more.

Open Sesame ⁹⁸

You've published 60% of your research in gold open access venues. This level of openness is matched by only 2% of researchers.

MENTIONS

160 online mentions
across 4 channels:

 2

PUBLICATIONS

 [Virtual R&D Teams: A New Model for Product Dev](#)
2015 *International Journal of Innovation*

25

 [A comparison between two main academic literatu](#)
[of science and scopus databases](#)
2013 *Asian Social Science*

Nader Ale Ebrahim

University of Malaya Visiting Research Fellow

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OVERVIEW

ACHIEVEMENTS

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[view all](#)

Open Access

★ Top 25%

82% of your research is free to read online. This level of availability puts you in the top 13% of researchers.

Global Reach

★ Top 25%

Your research has been saved and shared in 45 countries. That's high: only 12% of researchers get that much international attention.

 Countries include Argentina, Australia, Austria and 42 more.

ACTIVITY

961

Saves and shares across 5 channels:

774

167

10

8

2

PUBLICATIONS

[A comparison between two main academic literature collections: Web of science and scopus databases](#)

2013 *Asian Social Science*

162

Nader Ale Ebrahim

نادر آل ابراهيم

 Homepage

Artifact Summary

Nader Ale Ebrahim

نادر آل ابراهيم

[ResearcherID](#), [ORCID](#),

[The Berkeley Electronic Press™](#), [RePEc](#), [Google Scholar](#),
[Research tools](#), [Imgur](#), [Vizualize](#), [Quora](#), [Copernicus](#), [Diigo](#),
[How to write a review paper](#), [Twitter](#), [Archive](#), [Resume](#), [LinkedIn](#),
[Blogspot](#), [Postach.io](#), [Facebook](#), [About.me](#), [SCOPUS](#),
[ISDT Organizing Committee](#), [Ecademy](#), [Tumblr](#), [Vizify](#), [Informatik](#), [Wiki](#),
[The Effective Use of "Research Tools" and Resources – Training of Trainers \(TOT\)](#), [ResearcherID](#), [Peerevaluation](#),
[Best Virtual R&D Teams Papers](#), [Citec](#), [Methodspace](#), [Academic Research Microsoft](#), [PublicationsList](#), [WordPress](#), [Scoop.it](#),
[EduBlogs](#), [Managing Research Candidature](#), [Slid Share](#), [Science Wise](#), [Mendeley](#),
[The academic impact of research: Current and the future citation trends in developing countries](#), [Delicious](#),
[Practical Guide to Write a PhD Thesis and publish papers based on the thesis](#), [MPRA](#), [Research Tools Box](#), [CiteULike](#), [Zotero](#),
[ResearchGate](#), [arxiv](#), [Pearl Trees](#), [Enhancing Research Visibility and Improving Citations: Publication Marketing Tools](#), [Flickr](#),
[Target ISI Journals-HOW TO WRITE/PUBLISH ISI PAPERS](#), [Okkam](#), [ImpactStory](#), [My Web Site](#), [EPD 2010: 3 Minutes Competition](#),
[Social Science Research Network \(SSRN\)](#), [ORCID](#), [The Berkeley Electronic Press™](#), [Social Science Research Network \(SSRN\)](#),
[Homepage](#)

Artifact Summary

PlumX Metrics

USAGE
(views, downloads)

CAPTURES
(bookmarks, favorites, readers)

MENTIONS
(Wikipedia, comments, blogs)

SOCIAL MEDIA
(Facebook likes, shares, tweets)

CITATIONS
(Scopus, patents)

Analyze

You can aggregate metrics at any level to help you understand what is happening with your grant-funded research. For example you can see output and metrics by:

- Researcher
- Grant
- Department
- Journal

Metrics by publication year

In this example, it is apparent that citations (red bars) are a lagging indicator; there are substantially fewer citations in the recent years, especially 2013 and 2014. The other categories of metrics help you see what has been going on recently.

Public Library of Science (PLOS) Article-Level Metrics (ALMs)

At PLOS, we believe that research articles should primarily be judged on their individual merits, rather than on the basis of the journal in which they were published. In March 2009, we inaugurated a program to provide Article-Level Metrics (ALM) on every article across all journals. Article-Level Metrics (ALMs) capture the manifold ways in which research is disseminated and can help users determine the value of an article to them and to their scientific community. The regularly updated data include the following metrics:

Viewed PLOS Journals (HTML, PDF, XML) PubMed Central (HTML, PDF) Figshare (HTML, Downloads, Likes)	Saved Mendeley CiteULike	Discussed Twitter Facebook Wikipedia Reddit PLOS Comments ResearchBlogging ScienceSeeker Nature Blogs Wordpress.com	Recom- mended F1000Prime	Cited CrossRef Scopus Web of Science PubMed Central PMC Europe PMC Europe Database Links
--	---------------------------------------	---	--	--

Usage Count

Search My Tools ▾ Search History Marked

Results: 711
(from Web of Science Core Collection)

You searched for: **TITLE:** (virtual teams) ...[More](#)

[Create Alert](#)

Refine Results

Search within results for...

Web of Science Categories ▾

- MANAGEMENT (241)

Sort by: **Usage Count -- Since 2013** ▾

- Publication Date -- newest to oldest
- Publication Date -- oldest to newest
- Recently Added
- Times Cited -- highest to lowest
- Times Cited -- lowest to highest
- Usage Count -- Last 180 days
- Usage Count -- Since 2013**
- Relevance
- First Author -- A to Z

Page 1 of 7

Select [Print online](#) ▾

[Analyze Results](#)
[Create Citation Report](#)

1. [Management Learning: virtual teams across](#)
Jyrnma, Annukka
MANAGEMENT LEARNING Volume: 42 Issue: 4 Special Issue: SI Pages: 395-418 Published: SEP 2011

Times Cited: 11
(from Web of Science Core Collection)
Since 2013: 233 ▾

2. [Communication and trust in global virtual teams](#)
By: Jarvenpaa, SL; Leidner, DE
ORGANIZATION SCIENCE Volume: 10 Issue: 6 Pages:
Times Cited: 673
(from Web of Science Core Collection)

Elsevier journals

Top downloaded OA articles

ELSEVIER

Open Access

Here you'll find the most-downloaded Open Access Articles for Elsevier's journals.

- Agriculture Sciences
 - [Agriculture Science, General](#)
 - [Forest Science](#)
 - [Plant Science](#)
 - [Soil Science](#)
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